

URBAN GROUNDWATER CONTAMINATION BY RESIDUES OF UV FILTERS

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Abstract

The occurrence and fate of UV filters (UV F) in an urban aquifer in correlation with (1) the spatial distribution of UV F in Barcelona's groundwater, (2) the depth of the groundwater sample, (3) the physicochemical properties of the target compounds, (4) the recharge sources, and (5) the redox conditions of the Barcelona aquifers, were studied for the first time. The highest groundwater concentrations and the largest number of detected UV F were observed in an aquifer recharged by a polluted river (around 55 ng/L in SAP-4). In contrast, the urbanized areas had lower concentrations (around 20 ng/L in MPSP-1). Two pathways can be identified for UV F to enter the aquifers: (1) leakage of raw sewage from the sewage network in urbanized areas and (2) wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) effluents discharged into the river. Measured concentrations of UV F were significantly much lower than those estimated from the waste water proportion in groundwater samples suggesting that UV F might undergo transformation processes in both reducing and oxidizing conditions.

Keywords: UV filters, transformation products, aquifer contamination, urban groundwater, redox conditions

1. Introduction

UV filters (UV F) are chemical compounds that mitigate the deleterious effects of sunlight on both people and goods. They constitute a group of emerging environmental pollutants, potentially hazardous compounds that have been receiving steadily growing attention over the last decade as society has become aware of the dangerous effects of UV solar radiation. These compounds are produced and used in extremely large quantities worldwide (10,000 tons annually) in personal care products as well as in many industrial goods to protect products from photodegradation. Therefore, UV F might reach the environment endangering surface and groundwater bodies, both used for water supply purposes. Thus, UV F and their transformation products has become a subject of considerable concern.

UV F are widely used not only in sunscreens but also in a large number of cosmetics such as perfumes, shampoos, creams, among others. Their frequent use promote that these compounds enter the aquatic environment continuously, by direct inputs from aquatic recreational activities or mainly by indirect inputs through sewage waters. Once discharged from industrial and urban sources, they ultimately enter surface and ground waters, as they are not completely degraded in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Therefore, these compounds may have toxic effects on both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems since many of them accumulate in fish and invertebrates [1-3]. Their potential toxicity has been assessed in several studies, indicating that the majority have endocrine disrupting capacity (including all the herein studied benzophenone derivatives and 4-methylbenzylidenecamphor) [4-7]. Other adverse effects on fecundity and reproduction have also been determined in fish and rodents [6, 8]. Exposure to high levels of benzophenone derivatives UV F may be associated with oestrogen-dependent diseases as endometriosis in women [9].

UV F have been widely detected in surface waters [10-12], seawater [11, 13], wastewaters [10, 14, 15], and even tap water [16]. These compounds have also been determined at relevant concentrations in other environmental matrices as sewage sludge [17-19], sediments [20-22] and biota [3, 23], indicating that bioaccumulation of UV F is a fact and biomagnification may play an important role [3, 24]. Despite all this, to date there is no study that addressed the contamination of urban groundwater by UV F.

The objective of this study was to investigate the occurrence and fate of UV F in an urban aquifer in connection with (1) the spatial distribution of UV F in Barcelona's groundwater, (2) the depth of the groundwater sample, (3) the physicochemical properties of the target compounds, (4) the recharge sources, and (5) the redox conditions of the Barcelona aquifers. To this end, selected UV F and transformation products were analyzed in groundwater samples collected at three sites in the city of Barcelona in May and December 2010. We have selected these sampling sites because previous studies have reported the occurrence of other emerging organic pollutants such as pharmaceuticals [25] and drugs of abuse [26].

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Site description

The study area includes Barcelona and part of its metropolitan area located in north-eastern Spain. The area is placed between the Serra de Collserola (Catalan coastal ranges) and the Mediterranean Sea (Figure 1), both boundaries running approximately NNE–SSW. The Rivers Llobregat (SW) and Besòs (NE) constituted the other two boundaries. The climate in Barcelona is typically Mediterranean, with

extreme temperatures in January and August and a yearly average temperature of 15 °C. The average rainfall is of approximately 600 mm per year.

Currently, Barcelona's groundwater is used for secondary uses such as streets cleaning and to water plants and public gardens. However, it can be an important water supply resource because there are several aquifers below the city. These aquifers are characterized by their geological age (Figure 1). The Palaeozoic aquifer crops out at topographic highs to the NW, which consist of shales and granites. Quaternary and Tertiary aquifers are present in the rest of the city. The alluvial and deltaic sediments of the Rivers Llobregat and Besòs constituted the low topographic areas. Piedmont cones and coarse alluvial sediments are found in the intermediate areas.

2.2 Sampling

Thirty-two water samples were collected during two field campaigns in May 2010 (25 samples) and December 2010 (7 samples). Thirty-one samples were collected from groundwater and one sample was obtained from the River Besòs. The location of the observation points and the screen depths are displayed in Figure 1. Samples were collected in three different zones of the study area: (1) along Mallorca Street (MS) midway between the Collserola Range and the sea, (2) Poble Sec (PS) and (3) Besòs River Delta (BRD), where groundwater comes mainly from the river. All the groundwater samples were obtained after pumping a volume of at least three times that of the observation point. Field parameters measured in situ included electrical conductivity, pH, temperature and dissolved oxygen. Water samples for UV F analysis were measured continuously using a flow cell to avoid contact with

the air. The instruments were calibrated daily by means of standard solutions. Groundwater samples were collected after stabilization of field parameters and were not filtered in the field. They were stored in polyethylene terephthalate (PET) containers, which were amber in colour to avoid photodegradation, in a field refrigerator and taken to the laboratory at the end of the sampling day. Once there, samples were vacuum filtered through 1 μm glass fibre filters from Whatman (Fairfield, CT, USA), followed by 0.45 μm nylon membrane filters from Teknokroma (Barcelona, Spain), and stored in the dark at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis.

2.3 Standards and reagents

Table 1 summarizes the structures, CAS numbers and some relevant physicochemical properties of the selected target compounds.

Benzophenone-3 (BP3), 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone (BP1), 4-hydroxybenzophenone (4HB), benzophenone-4 (BP4), 4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone (4DHB) and ethyl-PABA (Et-PABA), were of the highest purity ($>99\%$) and were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany); 4-methylbenzylidenecamphor (4MBC, 99% purity) was supplied by Dr Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany); and benzophenone-2 (BP2) and 2,2'-Dihydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone (DHMB) (99%) by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The isotopically labelled compounds 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-2',3',4',5',6'-d₅ (BP3-d₅) and 3-(4-methylbenzylidene-d₄)camphor (4MBC-d₄), used as internal standards ($>99\%$), were obtained from CDN isotopes (Quebec, Canada). Methanol (MeOH), acetonitrile (ACN) and HPLC grade water (Lichrosolv), as well as formic acid (98% purity) were provided by Merck. N₂ and Ar purchased from Air Liquide (Barcelona, Spain) were of 99.995% purity.

Glass fiber F (1 μ m) and nylon membrane F (0.45 μ m) were obtained from Whatman International Ltd (Maidstone, England).

Individual stock standard solutions as well as the isotopically labelled internal stock standard solution were prepared on a weight basis in MeOH at 200 mg/L. The solutions were stored in the dark at -20 °C. A mixture standard solution at 20 mg/L in MeOH of each compound was prepared weekly. Working solutions were prepared daily by appropriate dilution of the mixture stock standard solution in MeOH.

2.4 Analytical methods

Analysis of the selected UV F and its transformation products were performed by on-line solid phase extraction coupled to liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (on-line-SPE-LC-MS/MS), following a fully automated method previously described by Gago-Ferrero et al. [27].

In this method preconcentration and purification of the samples (previously spiked with deuterated surrogate standards) as well as the chromatographic separation of their components were performed using an automated on-line SPE-LC device SymbiosisTM Pico from Spark Holland (Emmen, The Netherlands). On-line SPE preconcentration and purification of all samples, aqueous standard solutions and blanks was performed by loading 5 mL of the corresponding solutions through a PLRP-s cartridge previously conditioned with MeOH, ACN and HPLC water. After washing the cartridges with HPLC water, the trapped analytes are eluted to the LC column with the chromatographic mobile phase. For the further tandem mass (MS/MS) spectrometric detection under positive ionization (PI) mode the chromatographic mobile phase consisted of a mixture of HPLC water and ACN, both with 0.1% formic acid. In the negative ionization (NI) mode, the mobile phase

consisted of HPLC water containing 5 mM of ammonium acetate (pH 6.8). The chromatographic separation was achieved on a Hibar Purospher® STAR® HR R-18 ec. (50 mm × 2.0 mm, 5 µm) from Merck. MS/MS detection was performed using a 4000 Q TRAP™ MS/MS system from Applied Biosystems-Sciex (Foster City, California, USA). For improved sensitivity electrospray ionization (ESI) and selected reaction monitoring (SRM) mode were applied. Two major characteristic fragments of the precursor molecular ion ($[M+H]^+$ or $[M-H]^-$) were monitored per analyte to enhance method sensitivity and selectivity. The most abundant transition (based on peak areas) was used for quantification, whereas the second most abundant was used for confirmation. This procedure was in compliance with the European Council Directive 2002/657/EC, that although it was initially conceived for food residue analysis, it has been accepted by the scientific community for environmental analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Levels and spatial distribution of UV F in urban groundwater of Barcelona

The average concentration and the maximum levels of the target compounds measured in the groundwater samples analysed and their detection frequency are summarized in Table 2a. Figure 2 shows the measured concentrations in the observation points. No groundwater sample contained all the target compounds. Three out of the 9 target compounds, namely, DHMB, BP2 and Et-PABA, were not detected in any sample. The most ubiquitous compounds were BP3 and 4MBC, with detection frequencies of 32% and 29%, respectively. The remaining compounds were

detected in less than 16% of the samples. The highest concentrations corresponded to BP4 (36.6 ng/L at SAP-4), BP1 (19.4 ng/L at SAP-4) and BP3 (19.2 ng/L at ACO-2).

The study area was divided into the three aforementioned zones. The levels varied from one zone to another in terms of both concentrations and compounds detected (Table 2b). In the groundwater samples collected along MS (Z1), the compounds identified, ordered by decreasing frequency of detection, were BP3>BP1>4DHB=BP4. BP3 was the most frequently detected compound (71%) with an average concentration of 7.9 ng/L. BP1 was also frequently detected (41%) and the remaining compounds were only observed in one sample. Poble Sec was the area with the fewest UV F found in groundwater samples. The most commonly detected compound was BP3 (3 out of 12 samples) but the highest concentration detected corresponded to BP4 (19.2 ng/L at MPS-1). BP4 and 4MBC were detected only in one water sample. In Besòs River Delta, 5 out of the 9 target compounds were detected at least in one groundwater sample. The compounds identified in descending order were 4MBC>BP4>BP3=BP1>4HB. The most ubiquitous compound was 4MBC with a frequency of detection of 67% and at concentrations at the aquifer ranging from 7.64 to 13.9 ng/L. BP1 and BP3 were only found in 16 % of the samples near the river, with an average concentrations of 1.87 and 0.64 ng/L, respectively.

Overall, the highest groundwater concentrations (up to 56 ng/L in SAP-4) and the largest number of detected UV F were found in Besòs River Delta aquifers which are basically recharged by a river that receives large amounts of WWTPs effluents and whose final part courses through a heavily industrialised area of Barcelona. In contrast, the urbanized areas presented not only lower concentrations but also a much smaller number of compounds.

3.2 UV F profile according to groundwater depth

It was difficult to compare the occurrence of UV F considering the depth of the groundwater samples because the target compounds were not frequently detected and a given compound was also not detected in the multilayered observation points. Therefore, we decided to establish a comparison on the total amount of UV F in a given sample. The multilayered observation points that could be compared depending on the detection of the target compounds were: (1) GRA-2 (l) and GRA-3 (u), (2) ACO-1 (m), ACO-2 (l) and SV-8 (a), (3) PSP-5 (m) and PSP-6 (u), (4) PSP-7(m) and PSP-8 (u), (5) PSP-9 (m) and PSP-10 (u), (6) SAP-3 (m) and SAP-4 (u) and (7) SAP-1 (m) and SAP-2b (u) (see Figure 1). It was expected that the concentrations of UV F decreased with the screen depth of the groundwater sample, which suggests either some kinetically controlled removal process, as residence time generally increases with depth, or an increasing input of water free from UV F (i.e. water recharged in Collserola Range). This trend was evident in the multilayered observation points of Besòs River Delta zone. Both shallow observation points (SAP-2b and SAP-4) presented higher concentrations of UV F than their respective deep observation points (SAP-1 and SAP-3). UV F concentrations were null in SAP-3 and 56 ng/L in SAP-4 and 5.5 ng/L in SAP-1 and 18 ng/L in SAP-2b. In Besòs River Delta, this attenuation in depth might be attributed to removal processes such as redox reactions [28] or adsorption. However, this attenuation in depth was not obvious in Mallorca Street and Poble Sec. In Mallorca Street, all multilayered observation points displayed the opposite trend, the deeper the observation point, the higher the levels of UV F (Figure 3). The only compound that these multilayered points had in common was BP3. Although no significant differences were found,

BP3 presented always highest concentration in the deepest observation points (Figure 3). The deep observation points PSP-5 and PSP-9, located in Poble Sec, also presented highest concentrations of BP3 than their respective shallow points, but PSP-7 did not. Their presence in these aquifers might be related to leaking pipes from sewage system.

3.3 UV F mobility in the aquifer as function of their physicochemical properties

Among the properties summarized in Table 1, the octanol-water partition coefficient (K_{ow}) is usually used to predict the behaviour of organic contaminants in the environment. It is usually expressed as $\log K_{ow}$. In general, compounds with a lower $\log K_{ow}$ are supposed to be more mobile than those with a higher $\log K_{ow}$ [29]. Compounds with higher $\log K_{ow}$ usually tend to have high adsorption capacity especially onto organic matter [30]. However, in complex natural systems as aquifers, there are other relevant parameters, such as water pH, that control the proportion of ionized and non-ionized forms for a given compound. Consequently, K_{ow} may not be the most suitable parameter to properly predict the fate of the target compounds in environmental conditions [31]. Wells [32] emphasized the need to considering chemical ionogenicity and proposed D_{ow} (the pH dependent octanol–water distribution ratio), which is a combination of K_{ow} and pK_a , as a more appropriate physicochemical parameter to understand the mobility of a compound in environmentally relevant pH conditions. In this work, $\log D_{ow}$ have been used to identify the ionisable functional groups of the selected UV F at pH 7.5 since all groundwater samples collected were close to this pH (Table 1).

Based on these properties it was possible to assess the UV F mobility in the aquifer. The benzophenone BP3, its main derivative BP1 and their transformation

products 4DHB, 4HB and DHMB are mainly present in their neutral form in groundwater at pH 7.5. Although some proportions of the compounds BP1, 4DHB and 4HB might be present in their anionic form when their pK_{as} are 7.6, 7.8 and 8.1, respectively (Table 1). These anionic species correspond to the deprotonation of the hydroxyl groups of these compounds and minor changes in $\log D_{ow}$ values can be observed with respect to $\log K_{ow}$. Regarding BP2, at pH 7.5 neutral and anionic forms might be present in similar proportions (47% and 53%, respectively). Only BP4 is totally present in its anionic form at pH 7.5 and the $\log K_{ow}$ and $\log D_{ow}$ values are radically different (Table 1). The remaining compounds Et-PABA and 4MBC are neutral compounds.

The compounds that are found as neutral molecules do not interact with the negative charged minerals in aquifer materials. However, they possibly have sorption affinity with the amount of organic matter present in aquifer sediments, e.g. 4MBC, BP3 and DHMB, which present significant $\log K_{ow}$ values (4.92, 3.86 and 3.41, respectively). The compounds that have an anionic proportion might have a more hydrophilic character and, generally exhibit lower $\log D_{ow}$ values (for neutral compounds $\log K_{ow}$ values are equal than $\log D_{ow}$ ones). To sum up, different mobility is expected for the UV F in aquifers. The most mobile compound might be the benzophenone BP4 followed by BP2 and 4DHB. In contrast, 4MBC, BP3 and DHMB are expected to be the less mobile.

3.4 Occurrence of the target compounds related to aquifers recharges sources

The UV F occurrence in the urban groundwater of Barcelona likely depends on the recharge sources feeding these aquifers. Jurado et al. [26] evaluated the proportion in which the different recharge sources contributed to the resident water of the Mallorca Street, Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta aquifers. In the groundwater samples collected along Mallorca Street, the clean water recharge from Collserola Range was the main source contributing to the total resident water (60%), especially in the deep observation points such as ACO-1 and GRA-2. The remaining 40% were leaks from sewage (31%) and water supply (9%) networks. In Poble Sec, the main contributors were network sewage and water supply leaks, accounting for 96% (50% and 46%, respectively) and the remaining 4% corresponded to rainfall infiltration. Finally, the River Besòs was by far the largest contributor to the total recharge in Besòs River Delta aquifers, representing 91%. The remaining 9% corresponded to sewage network and water supply leaks. Based on these results, two main pathways could be identified for UV F to enter to the aquifers studied: (1) leakage from sewage network which contains influents from WWTPs in the urban groundwater from Mallorca Street and Poble Sec aquifers and (2) WWTPs effluents discharged to the River Besòs in the River Besòs Delta aquifer. Other minor pathways in Mallorca Street and Poble Sec aquifers can be loss from water supply network since BP3 and 4MBC has been detected in tap waters in Barcelona city and the surrounding metropolitan area [16]. Despite loss from water supply represented nearly half of the resident water in Poble Sec aquifers, its contribution to the contamination is less significant than those from sewage network because the latter presents higher concentrations (Table 3).

Based on the identified recharge sources in resident water of Barcelona aquifers, the occurrence of the UV F was compared with some common tracers of the sewage water such as nitrate and ammonium [33]; and also to the trihalomethane chloroform, which is a by-product commonly found in drinking water treatment disinfected with chlorine [34]. The spatial distribution for selected generic tracers and the target compounds is shown in Figure 2. The samples located in the Barcelona Plain aquifers (Mallorca Street and Poble Sec zones) presented high levels of nitrate and low or null levels of ammonium with 0.26 mg/L in GRA-2 being the maximum concentration. Only the samples of the deepest piezometers ACO-1, GRA-2, MODEL and SO-30 had levels of nitrate below 25 mg/L. The rest of the observation points exceeded 50 mg/L. Regarding chloroform; it was detected in all groundwater samples in concentrations up to 23 µg/L. Conversely, Besòs River Delta groundwater presented low nitrate levels and ammonium was present in significant concentrations. All groundwater samples exceeded 1.5 mg/L of ammonium and chloroform was not detected in any of the samples. Based on these tracers, the occurrence of the target compounds in the Mallorca Street and Poble Sec aquifers might be mainly related to network sewage loss. In the Besòs River Delta aquifer, the inefficient removal in WWTPs of some UV F, namely BP1, BP2 and BP4, can be the main source of these compounds in the aquifer because WWTPs effluents are directly discharged into the River Besòs. It is important to mention that groundwater concentrations were lower than the reported WWTPs values for both influents and effluents in the UV F studies (Table 3). This suggested that their depletion in the aquifers might be attributed to removal processes such as physical adsorption, biological degradation and/or dilution effects.

3.5 Redox conditions of the aquifers

The fate of organic pollutants in the aquifers depends on several factors such as the aquifer lithology, the physicochemical properties of a given compound and the redox state of the aquifer. Among these factors, the redox state of the aquifer appears to play an important role in the natural removal of the organic compounds in the aquifers. In this study the three zones selected had different redox conditions. The Poble Sec and Mallorca aquifers were oxic, as demonstrated by redox indicators such as low or null levels of ammonium (on average 0.03 mg/L) and significant levels of dissolved oxygen and nitrate (on average 4 mg/L, and 95.7 mg/L, respectively). Reducing conditions were suggested in the Besòs River Delta aquifer by the presence of ammonium (4.3 mg/L, on average) and the low or null levels of dissolved oxygen and nitrate (on average 1.2 mg/L, and 4.4 mg/L, respectively). In fact, Jurado et al. [28] previously identified the occurrence of redox processes such as aerobic respiration, denitrification and sulphate reduction in the Besòs River Delta aquifers.

Only compounds detected in more than 15% of groundwater samples (see Table 2a) are discussed in this study (BP1, BP3, BP4 and 4MBC). The average concentration of the parent compound BP3 in raw sewage water was between 300-400 ng/L (Table 3). Also BP3 was detected in Barcelona tap water in concentrations up to 295 ng/L [16]. If only recharge from sewage network loss was considered, the expected concentrations in groundwater might be in the range 90-120 ng/L in Mallorca Street and 150-200 ng/L in Poble sec aquifers. However, the measured concentrations of BP3 in these observation points were significantly lower than those expected from the recharge from sewage network loss. BP3 concentrations in groundwater samples collected along the Mallorca Street and Poble Sec aquifers were one order of magnitude lower than raw sewage water. The same evaluation for

BP1, BP4 and the camphor derivative 4MBC, which were found at significant levels in raw sewage water, suggested that these compounds may be removed in the aquifer under the oxic conditions of the groundwater.

As mentioned before, in the Besòs River Delta aquifer the main water contributor are the WWTPs effluents. The concentrations in the WWTPs effluents are significantly lower than those of the influents (see Table 3). It would be anticipated that measured concentration in the aquifer should be lower than in oxic aquifers. This was the case for BP3, its transformation product BP1, and BP4 which were only detected in two samples and at lower concentrations than in the river (Figure 4). These UV F appeared to be removed under the reducing conditions of the Besòs River Delta groundwater because: (1) they were poorly detected in the observation points and (2) presented lower levels than those of the river (Figure 4). The highest concentrations of BP1 and BP4 were found in the shallow piezometers located near the river (SAP-4 and SAP-2b, Figure 1) and not detected in the rest of the aquifer. This possibly indicates that natural attenuation may occur in aquifers due to physical (adsorption) and biochemical degradation (redox processes) [35]. Only the camphor derivative 4MBC was widely detected in the aquifer and in concentrations similar or even higher than those from the river (Table 2b), which suggests that this compound was more persistent than the other UV F in the aquifer. The relatively high K_{ow} of 4MBC may suggest that sorption is less important.

To summarise, based on the data collected, UV F aquifer concentrations were generally much lower than those expected due to dilution, as evaluated from the recharge sources. This suggests that these compounds seem to be removed in the aquifer under different redox conditions: oxidizing conditions in the samples collected along Mallorca Street and Poble Sec and reducing conditions in Besòs

River Delta. Only 4MBC, despite having a high $\log K_{ow}$ value, was less affected than the other UV F by removal processes under the reducing conditions in Besòs River Delta aquifers. This points out that further research is required to properly assess UV F fate in aquifers.

4. Conclusions

The present study reported for the first time urban groundwater contamination by UV F residues. The following conclusions may be drawn from this study:

(1) Groundwater in Barcelona aquifers contains UV F in low but measurable concentrations. Although not frequently detected, aquifers from the Besòs River Delta were found to be the most polluted in terms of UV filter compounds. This might be attributed to the fact that the River Besòs receives large amounts of WWTPs effluents. Also, they were detected in urbanised areas such as Mallorca Street and Poble Sec but at lower concentrations.

(2) Attenuation of these compounds in depth was observed in the Besòs River Delta aquifer but not in groundwater samples collected along Mallorca Street. In Poble Sec a clear pattern was not found because it varied depending on the observation points.

(3) UV F presented different mobility in aquifers depending on their physicochemical properties: (a) neutral molecules with significant $\log K_{ow}$ values are less mobile because they might exhibit sorption affinity with the amount of organic matter present in aquifer sediments, e.g. 4MBC, BP3 and DHMB and (b) compounds that have an anionic proportion might have a more hydrophilic character and might be more mobile, e.g. BP4 followed by BP2 and 4DHB.

(4) Concentrations in the aquifer were generally much lower than those expected from simple mixing of the different recharge sources that contributed to the occurrence of UV F in groundwater. This observation suggested that the removal of UV F in the aquifer may occur under different redox conditions.

(5) Natural attenuation may therefore be significant in the removal of UV F from the aquifers. Further investigation is necessary to elucidate this observation, including identification and structural characterization of the transformation products formed in order to assess the potential environmental risk posed for such derivatives.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. On the left, schematic description of the hydrogeology of Barcelona: (1a) Llobregat Delta made up of gravels, sands, silts and clays (Holocene, Quaternary), (1b) Besòs Delta composed of gravels, sands, silts and clays (Holocene, Quaternary), (1c) Barcelona Plain consisting of carbonated clays (Pleistocene, Quaternary), (2) Barcelona Plain made up of marls, sandstones and sands (Tertiary) and (3) Collserola Range consisting of shale and granites (Palaeozoic). On the right, a piezometric map of the case study zone, this is divided into three areas: Mallorca Street, Poble Sec and (Z3) Besòs River Delta. The contour intervals are 2 m (continuous purple line), for heads ranging from 5 to below 25 m (continuous blue line) and 25 m above (continuous black line). At the bottom, observation points on each zone, including the depth of the screen: (u) upper, (m) middle, (l) lower and (a) totally screened.

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of the six detected compounds, ammonium, nitrate and Chloroform in Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta aquifers.

Figure 3. Total UV filters (ng/L) and nitrate (mg/L) concentrations for some multilayered piezometers.

Figure 4. Concentrations of selected UV F (ng/L) in the recharge sources and in the aquifers of the urbanized areas of Mallorca Street and Poble Sec and in Besòs River Delta zone.

Table captions

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of the target compounds.^a INCI (International Nomenclature for Cosmetic Ingredient) elaborated by CTFA and COLIPA.^b ACD/I-Lab predicted values calculated using Advanced Chemistry Development software (ACD/Labs, 1996-2013).

K_{ow} , partition coefficient octanol-water; D_{ow} , pH-dependent partition coefficient octanol-water; Neu, neutral; Neg, negative

Table 2. Detection frequency (%), number of positive samples towards total analysed samples (in parenthesis), and average and maximum concentration (ng/L) of UV F and transformation products measured in **(a)** Barcelona urban groundwater and **(b)** detailed in each zone of the study area (Mallorca Street, Poble Sec and Besòs River Delta zones). * BP4 was analyzed in 4, 10 and 12 samples, respectively.

Table 3. Occurrence of UV F in influents and effluents of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) and in tap water (River Llobregat). References: ¹ Kasprzyk-Hodern et al. [36]; ² Wick et al. [37]; ³ Rodil et al. [12]; ⁴ Pedrouzo et al. [38] and ⁵ Díaz-Cruz et al. [16].